

Expressions of the Smarandache Coprime Function

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Smarandache Coprime Function is defined this way:

$$C_k(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k \text{ are coprime numbers} \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

We see two expressions of the Smarandache Coprime Function for $k=2$.

EXPRESSION 1:

$$C_2(n_1, n_2) = -E \left[\frac{n_1 n_2 - lcm(n_1, n_2)}{n_1 n_2} \right]$$

$E(x)$ = the biggest integer number smaller or equal than x .

If n_1, n_2 are coprime numbers:

$$lcm(n_1, n_2) = n_1 n_2 \Rightarrow C_2(n_1, n_2) = -E \left[\frac{0}{n_1 n_2} \right] = 0$$

If n_1, n_2 aren't coprime numbers:

$$lcm(n_1, n_2) < n_1 n_2 \Rightarrow 0 < \frac{n_1 n_2 - lcm(n_1, n_2)}{n_1 n_2} < 1 \Rightarrow C_2(n_1, n_2) = 1$$

EXPRESSION 2:

$$C_2(n_1, n_2) = 1 - E \left[\frac{\prod_{\substack{d | n_1 \\ d > 1}} \prod_{\substack{d' | n_2 \\ d' > 1}} |d - d'|}{\prod_{d|n_1} \prod_{d'|n_2} (d + d')} \right]$$

If n_1, n_2 are coprime numbers then $d \neq d' \quad \forall d, d' \neq 1$

$$\Rightarrow 0 < \frac{\prod_{\substack{d | n_1 \\ d > 1}} \prod_{\substack{d' | n_2 \\ d' > 1}} |d - d'|}{\prod_{d|n_1} \prod_{d'|n_2} (d + d')} < 1 \Rightarrow C_2(n_1, n_2) = 0$$

If n_1, n_2 aren't coprime numbers $\exists d = d' \quad d > 1, d' > 1 \Rightarrow C_2(n_1, n_2) = 1$
Smarandache coprime function for $k \geq 2$.

$$C_k(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k) = -E \left[\frac{1}{GCD(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)} - 1 \right]$$

If $n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k$ are coprime numbers:

$$GCD(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k) = 1 \Rightarrow C_k(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k) = 0$$

If $n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k$ aren't coprime numbers: $GCD(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k) > 1$

$$0 < \frac{1}{GCD} < 1 \Rightarrow -E \left[\frac{1}{GCD} - 1 \right] = 1 = C_k(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$$

References:

1. E. Burton, "Smarandache Prime and Coprime Functions"
2. F. Smarandache, "Collected Papers", Vol. II, 200 p.,p. 137, Kishinev University Press.